

Deliverable title / Report title

JRP7 - LISTADAPT

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Responsible Partner: xxxx

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Join Integrative/Research Project	JRP7 - LISTADAPT
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Other contributors	
Due month of the deliverable	
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Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	

Title

subtitle

Work package x